

THE SCIENTIFIC THEORETICAL ANALYSIS TO CREATE BRIDGE BETWEEN ORGANIC CHEMISTRY AND MANUFACTURING TECHNOLOGY

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Abstract. *In this thesis, investigations were conducted to sustain the bright future of young people through collaborative programs and contemporary methods*

Keywords: *Anthropology, theory classification, indicators, pedagogical technique, joint preparation.*

НАУЧНО-ТЕОРЕТИЧЕСКИЙ АНАЛИЗ ДЛЯ СОЗДАНИЯ МОСТА МЕЖДУ ОРГАНИЧЕСКОЙ ХИМИЕЙ И ПРОИЗВОДСТВЕННОЙ ТЕХНОЛОГИЕЙ

Аннотация. *В этой диссертации были проведены исследования, направленные на улучшение светлого будущего молодых людей с помощью совместных программ и современных методов.*

Ключевые слова: *Антропология, классификация теории, индикаторы, педагогическая техника, совместная подготовка.*

RESEARCH AND METHODS:

One of the best well-known method is cluster which have been using in some famous developing countries. Cluster system was originated in anthropology by Driver and Kroeber in 1932 and introduced to psychology by Joseph Zubin in 1938 and Robert Tryon in 1939 and also famously used by Cattell beginning in 1943 for trait theory classification in personality psychology. Cluster system contains all of the branch of items to explain more efficiently and like spider's web all of the different systems are linked each other.

Nowadays, the numbers of gas oil plants are increasing and finding suitable, good employees is one of important task for them. Recent studies have pointed out the urgent need for future technologists and mentally workers to adopt teaching plan in order to be prepared to cope with the increasing industrial requirements of the plants of the future. Some methods are invented to solve this problem.

Furthermore, universities also want to see bright future of their graduates. Some people say that manufacturing is totally different from teaching programs and invisible knowledge which is taught now and students only get really knowledge by seeing or touching in plants. Despite of these facts, universities are source of initially skills of technologically settlements, indicators, measurements, processes and etc. Professors try to teach students by easy ways and practice.

As everybody knows, some useful methods have been using to adopt teaching and technologically processes and improve learning pedagogical techniques in universities. Prevent boring things during the learning time and change difficulties to easier one's is the one of the best benefits of methods. Methods contain interesting shapes, words, unusual things, games and so others help students. These methods attract attentions, contribute learning ability, also develop teaching techniques.

In organic chemistry, it is really vital that understands more about chemical reactions' mechanisms and teaches to the students to be a good engineer or laborant in plants. So, we can show dependings from university programmms until to get engineer skills. Some scholars and chemical technology leaders realize that how this thesis and methods are important to get a high-skill workers. Now, majority of plants are related to chemistry science, especially organic department so this bridge is needed us.

I would like to say some opinions to improve this method and build a bridge between education and manufacturing process are: plants share their useful materials an according to relatively subjects and university teachers should use these materials to their initial students. After this process, we will obtain majority of ready and knowledgeable graduates to work in plants. Increase cooperation systems between educational institutions and plants. Knowledge and opinions of youngsters may aid to solve plant problems for example: difficult chemical reaxim mechanisms or highly scientific theoretical problems if they would have or happen. Young students playing a main role to build bridge and learn directly from university systems to become a good engineer. Organize continuously training courses in universities should be the best perform and understandable lessons for young students what is the purpose of cluster methods and systems.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION:

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CONCLUSION:

Our university education process , this system worked very well and showed a high efficiency, which was over 30 % better than pupils had used before. In addition, talented students gave some wonderful ideas to develop it. As we can see, youngsters playing a basic role during this method will be using.

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